

Studies on the Effect of Different Constituents of Soil Humic Acid in the Formation of Clay-humus Complexes

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The effect of the different constituents of soil humic acid in the formation of clay-humus complexes has been studied by potentiometric titrations as well as by analytical methods. It has been found that simpler components of humic acid, separated by ethanol extraction, viz., 'pure' humic acid and hymatomelanic acid, show a greater interaction in presence of metal ions than crude humic acid. This may be due to greater physical accessibility of the interacting groups and hence a much easier co-ordination. The two fractions, however, are equally effective in forming clay-humus complex, although their exchange capacities are different.

Humus is believed to be a mixture of several groups of chemical complexes, defined by certain common and characteristic properties. From each group several different well-defined organic compounds, such as hydrocarbons, aldehydes and ketones, amino-acids, carbohydrates, etc., have been isolated by various workers. According to Oden¹, the soil humus can be separated into four groups of organic complexes shown in the following scheme.

Many of the workers investigating on the function of humus in the physical or physico-chemical soil complex made no distinction between humus and humic acid. Very few studies were made with humus as a whole; in the majority of cases, the organic materials used were only "humic acid" preparations obtained by extraction of soil organic matter with alkali solutions and precipitation with acids. Practically nothing is known concerning the effect of the various constituents of humic acid in the clay-humus combinations. Waksman²

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1. *Kolloid-chem. Beih.*, 1919, 11, 75.

2. "Humus" Bailliere, Tindall & Co, London, 1938.

and Gillam³ gained evidence that lignin-like substances were present in humus; McCalla⁴ and Alderfer *et al.*⁵ have shown that such substances are capable of aggregating soils. Swaby⁶ also studied the influence of humus on soil aggregation and the relative cementing power of various humus fractions, but his attempt to fractionate humic acid into its component colloidal cements was unsuccessful. In the present investigation the crude humic acid, extracted from soil by alkali treatment and followed by precipitation with acid, has been separated into two important constituents, as stated before, and the effect of each on the clay-organic matter complexes has been studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

Electrodialysed crude humic acid (SHm), extracted from Siliguri soil (from Darjeeling, West Bengal) by the usual method, was first concentrated on a water bath, and then soxhleted with absolute ethanol. The hot ethanol was circulated through the whole mass until the ethanolic extract became colorless. The insoluble part, the 'pure' humic acid, was freed of ethanol and dispersed in water. The ethanol-soluble part, hymatomelanic acid, was then dried on a water bath and dispersed in water. In this way the two constituents of humic acid, namely, 'pure' humic acid and hymatomelanic acid sols, have been prepared. The base-exchange capacity of each of these fractions was determined potentiometrically from their inflection points by titration with a standard baryta solution. These were then mixed with CI clay (illitic) exactly as in the experiments with crude humic acid⁷. In the present investigation, the effect of two fractions of crude humic acid was followed by potentiometric titrations⁷ as well as by estimating the amount of non-extractable organic matter from their mixtures in the alkali leachate⁸. The results are recorded in Tables I—V. A representative curve is shown in Fig. 1.

TABLE I

Base-exchange capacity of 'pure' humic acid and hymatomelanic acid by potentiometric titration.

Substance taken.	B.e.c. (m.e./100 g.) (from inflection).	pH at inflection.	% Crude SHm.
'Pure' humic acid	340	7.9	44
Hymatomelanic acid	555	8.2	56

From the percentage composition of the two fractions, the calculated b.e.c. of crude SHm in me/100 g. is 460. This value is in good agreement with the experimental value 450 me/100 g. (Sen⁷).

3. *Soil Sci.*, 1940, 49, 433.

4. *Ibid.*, 1945, 59, 287.

5. *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1944, 36, 272.

6. *J. Soil Sci.*, 1949, 1, 182.

7. Sen, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1960, 23, 145.

8. Sen, *this Journal*, 1960, 37, 793.

TABLE II

Base-exchange capacity of CI clay—'pure' humic acid mixtures.

B. e. c. of CI clay = 55 m.e./100g.

B. e. c. of 'pure' humic acid = 340 m.e./100g.

Ratio of humic acid: clay.	pH at inflection.	Calc.	B. e. c. (m. e. / 100 g.).		Diff.
			Found.		
1 : 10	8.0	81	77		4 (0)
1 : 20	7.9	69	63		6 (9)
1 : 40	7.8	62	54		8 (11.8)
1 : 60	7.8	60	49		11 (16)

N. B. Figures in parentheses indicate values with the crude SHm-CI clay mixtures⁷.

TABLE III

Base-exchange capacity of the CI clay—hymatomelanic acid mixtures.

B. e. c. of CI clay = 55 m.e./100g. B. e. c. of hymatomelanic acid = 555 m.e./100 g.

Ratio of hymatomelanic acid: clay.	pH at inflection.	Calc.	B. e. c. (m. e. / 100 g.).		Diff.
			Found.		
1 : 10	8.0	100.5	96		4.5 (6)
1 : 20	8.0	79.0	72		7 (9)
1 : 40	7.8	68.0	59		9 (11.0)
1 : 60	7.8	63.0	51		12 (16)

TABLE IV

Estimation of alkali-extractable humic acid from CI clay—'pure' humic acid mixtures.

Ions present.	'Pure' humic acid: clay.	Humic acid taken.	Humic acid in N_2CO_3 extract.	Humic acid combined.	
H^+	1 : 10	0.060 g.	0.0420 g.	0.0180 g.	30% (20)
	1 : 20	0.030	0.0198	0.0102	34 (25)
	1 : 40	0.016	0.0100	0.0060	39 (29)
	1 : 60	0.010	0.0058	0.0042	42 (35)
Ca^{2+}	1 : 10	0.060	0.0384	0.0216	36 (28)
	1 : 20	0.030	0.0174	0.0126	42 (33)
	1 : 40	0.016	0.0083	0.0077	48 (40)
	1 : 60	0.010	0.0045	0.0055	55 (46)
Mg^{2+}	1 : 10	0.060	0.0324	0.0276	46 (35)
	1 : 20	0.030	0.0144	0.0156	52 (42)
	1 : 40	0.016	0.0061	0.0097	61 (47)
	1 : 60	0.010	0.0033	0.0067	67 (55)
Al^{3+}	1 : 10	0.060	0.0336	0.0264	44 (35)
	1 : 20	0.030	0.0114	0.0156	52 (40)
	1 : 40	0.016	0.0061	0.0099	62 (46)
	1 : 60	0.010	0.0034	0.0066	66 (54)
Fe^{3+}	1 : 10	0.060	0.0330	0.0270	45 (37.5)
	1 : 20	0.030	0.0144	0.0156	52 (44)
	1 : 40	0.016	0.0066	0.0094	59 (48)
	1 : 60	0.010	0.0032	0.0068	68 (58)

N. B. Figures in parentheses indicate values with crude SHm-CI clay mixtures⁸.

TABLE V

Estimation of alkali-extractable hymatomelanic acid from CI clay—hymatomelanic acid mixture.

Ions present.	Hymatomelanic acid : clay.	Hymatomelanic acid.			
		Taken.	In Na ₂ CO ₃ extract.	Combined (found).	
H ⁺	1 : 10	0.060 g.	0.0420 g.	0.0160 g.	30% (20)
	1 : 20	0.030	0.0201	0.0099	33 (25)
	1 : 40	0.015	0.0094	0.0056	37 (29)
	1 : 60	0.010	0.0060	0.0040	40 (35)
Ca ²⁺	1 : 10	0.060	0.0390	0.0210	35 (28)
	1 : 20	0.030	0.0174	0.0126	42 (35)
	1 : 40	0.015	0.0081	0.0069	46 (40)
	1 : 60	0.010	0.0050	0.0050	50 (46)
Mg ²⁺	1 : 10	0.060	0.0340	0.0260	45 (35)
	1 : 20	0.030	0.0156	0.0144	48 (42)
	1 : 40	0.015	0.0066	0.0064	56 (47)
	1 : 60	0.010	0.0040	0.0060	60 (55)
Al ³⁺	1 : 10	0.060	0.0330	0.0270	45 (35)
	1 : 20	0.030	0.0144	0.0156	52 (40)
	1 : 40	0.015	0.0060	0.0090	60 (46)
	1 : 60	0.010	0.0036	0.0064	64 (54)
Fe ³⁺	1 : 10	0.060	0.0336	0.0264	44 (37.5)
	1 : 20	0.030	0.0150	0.0150	50 (44)
	1 : 40	0.015	0.0063	0.0087	58 (48)
	1 : 60	0.010	0.0037	0.0063	63 (58)

N.B. Figures in parentheses indicate values with crude SHm-CI clay mixtures⁶.

DISCUSSION

Table I shows that the b.e.c. of hymatomelanic acid fraction is greater than that of the 'pure' humic acid fraction. This clearly indicates the presence of excess phenolic group in the former fraction, because it has been found that the -OH groups of soil humus contribute more than the -COOH groups towards the exchange property⁹. But both the fractions lower the b.e.c. of the clay-humus mixtures more or less to the same extent, which has been shown in Tables II and III. The amounts of 'pure' humic acid as well as of hymatomelanic acid, retained by the clay minerals in presence of H⁺ ion and other metal ions, are greater than those with the crude humic acid, as found from the Tables IV and V. The two fractions, however, are equally effective in forming clay-humus complex, although their exchange capacities differ.

FIG. 1. pH-titration curves of two fractions of crude SHm.

The greater capacity of the separated components to form clay-metal ion-humus complexes is perhaps due to the availability of a larger number of linkages for co-ordination.

There are relatively a large number of -OH groups and -COOH groups in humatomelanic acid and the 'pure' humic acid, respectively, available for co-ordination. But probably because of the co-ordinating power of -COOH groups being stronger than the -OH groups, the percentage of the two components combining with the clay is not much different. In the original crude humic acid (SHm), the available co-ordinating linkages appear to be appreciably less than in the two components separately. Consequently, the percentage of crude humic acid combined to the clay, specially in presence of metal ions, is also less.

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